

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING STARTUP DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AMONG THE YOUNG GENERATION

Usmonkhujayeva Nigina G'ofur qizi

Assistant, IMC KREMS Transnational Department,

Tashkent State University of Economics

ravshanovanigi@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0007-8870-9530

Abstract. This study investigates the key determinants influencing startup development in Uzbekistan, an emerging economy with a rapidly evolving entrepreneurial ecosystem. Drawing on a structured survey of young individuals engaged in startup activities, the research examines the impact of access to finance, government support, entrepreneurial characteristics, and market-related factors on startup success. Using quantitative methods, the study identifies statistically significant relationships between these variables and startup growth potential. The findings highlight the critical role of financial resources, strategic planning, and institutional support in enhancing startup sustainability. The study contributes to the limited empirical literature on entrepreneurship in Central Asia and offers practical implications for policymakers and aspiring entrepreneurs.

Key words: startup development, entrepreneurship, Uzbekistan, emerging economies, access to finance, government support, market research, quantitative analysis.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot tadbirkorlik ekotizimi jadal rivojlanayotgan O'zbekistonda startaplarni rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillarni o'rganadi. Startap faoliyati bilan shug'ullanuvchi yoshlar o'rtasida o'tkazilgan tuzilgan so'rovnoma asosida tadqiqot moliyalashtirish imkoniyatlari, davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash, tadbirkorlik xususiyatlari va bozor omillarining startap muvaffaqiyatiga ta'sirini tahlil qiladi. Miqdoriy usullar yordamida ushbu o'zgaruvchilar va startaplarning o'sish salohiyati o'rtasidagi statistik jihatdan ahamiyatli bog'liqliklar aniqlandi. Natijalar startap barqarorligini oshirishda moliyaviy resurslar, strategik rejalashtirish va institutsional yordamning muhim rolini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot Markaziy Osiyoda tadbirkorlik bo'yicha mavjud cheklangan empirik adabiyotlarga hissa qo'shadi hamda siyosat yurituvchilar va yosh tadbirkorlar uchun amaliy tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: startap rivojlanishi, tadbirkorlik, O'zbekiston, rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlar, moliyalashtirish imkoniyati, davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash, bozor tadqiqotlari, miqdoriy tahlil.

Аннотация. Данное исследование изучает ключевые факторы, влияющие на развитие стартапов в Узбекистане — развивающейся экономике с быстро формирующейся предпринимательской экосистемой. На основе структурированного опроса молодых людей, занимающихся стартап-деятельностью, исследование рассматривает влияние доступа к финансированию, государственной поддержки, предпринимательских характеристик и рыночных факторов на успех стартапов. С помощью количественных методов выявлены статистически значимые взаимосвязи между этими переменными и потенциалом роста стартапов. Результаты подчеркивают важную роль финансовых ресурсов, стратегического планирования и институциональной поддержки в повышении устойчивости стартапов. Исследование вносит вклад в ограниченную эмпирическую литературу по предпринимательству в Центральной Азии и предлагает практические рекомендации для политиков и начинающих предпринимателей.

Ключевые слова: развитие стартапов, предпринимательство, Узбекистан, развивающиеся экономики, доступ к финансированию, государственная поддержка, исследование рынка, количественный анализ.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship has become a fundamental driver of economic growth, innovation, and employment creation in the global economy. Startups, in particular, play a pivotal role in introducing new technologies and business models, thereby increasing competitiveness and economic diversification. In emerging economies

such as Uzbekistan, the development of startups is still at an early stage, making it essential to identify the factors that contribute to their success and sustainability.

Despite growing interest in entrepreneurship, startups face numerous challenges, including limited access to finance, insufficient institutional support, and a lack of managerial experience. These constraints are especially pronounced in transition economies, where market systems and regulatory frameworks continue to evolve.

This study aims to quantitatively examine the factors influencing startup development in Uzbekistan. Specifically, it focuses on measurable variables such as financial availability, government support, entrepreneurial experience, and market research practices. By applying statistical analysis, the research seeks to test the relationships between these variables and startup outcomes, thereby providing empirical evidence to support policy formulation and strategic decision-making.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship is commonly defined as the process of identifying opportunities and organizing resources under conditions of uncertainty to create value [1]. Startups represent a specific form of entrepreneurial activity characterized by innovation, scalability, and high growth potential [2]. However, empirical studies indicate that a significant proportion of startups encounter difficulties due to internal and external constraints [3].

Access to financial resources is widely recognized as a critical factor in startup development. Prior studies demonstrate that the availability of capital positively influences both the decision to start a business and its subsequent growth [4]. Various financing sources, including venture capital, business angels, and crowdfunding, provide essential support at different stages of the startup lifecycle.

The institutional environment plays a crucial role in shaping entrepreneurial activity. Government policies, regulatory frameworks, and support programs can either facilitate or hinder startup development [5]. Empirical evidence suggests that favorable institutional conditions significantly increase entrepreneurial intention and firm performance [6].

Human capital, including education, skills, and prior experience, is another important determinant of entrepreneurial success. Research indicates that individuals with higher levels of education and business experience are more likely to successfully establish and grow startups [7].

Gender and social context have been shown to influence entrepreneurial activity. While some studies report higher participation rates among men [8], others emphasize the importance of cultural and institutional factors in shaping these differences.

Internationalization offers startups opportunities for expansion and increased profitability but also introduces additional risks [9]. Startups with a global orientation tend to achieve higher growth rates, provided they possess the necessary capabilities.

The literature identifies several measurable determinants of startup development, including financial access, institutional support, human capital, and market strategies. These factors form the basis for empirical testing in this study and contribute to a deeper understanding of entrepreneurship in emerging economies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative research design to examine the factors influencing startup development in Uzbekistan. A survey-based approach was selected to collect standardized data and enable statistical analysis of relationships between variables.

Quantitative research is appropriate for this study as it allows for the measurement of key constructs such as financial access, government support, and entrepreneurial behavior, while also facilitating generalization across a broader population.

Primary data were collected using a structured online questionnaire developed through Google Forms. The questionnaire consisted of 18 questions, including both closed-ended and limited open-ended items to capture measurable responses.

The survey targeted young individuals involved in or interested in startups, as they represent the primary population engaged in entrepreneurial activities in Uzbekistan.

A total of 57 respondents participated in the study. The questionnaire was distributed through:

- social networks (Telegram, Instagram);
- personal contacts and referrals.

Before full distribution, the questionnaire was pilot-tested on a small group to ensure clarity, relevance, and logical structure.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To address the research question, this questionnaire was conducted. The information obtained was analyzed using graphs and textual interpretation. Based on the survey results, recommendations and conclusions are presented.

The survey included questions about business ideas, reasons for interest in this field, investments and finance, as well as factors that contribute to the development or challenges of startups in Uzbekistan.

The total number of individuals who completed the online questionnaire was 57 respondents. Of these, 34 were men, accounting for 59.6% of the total, and 23 were women, accounting for 40.4%. This indicates that men demonstrated higher participation and interest in business startups within the survey sample.

Since the questionnaire was created for a specific group of people, namely young people, the results are also consistent with this. 77.2 percent of all respondents chose the category from 18 to 24 years old, while the other 21.1 percent of respondents were in the 25–34 age category, and only 1 respondent was under the age of 18 (Figure 1).

Why do you want to create your own startup project?

Figure 1. Creation of Startup Projects¹

It was important to identify how many respondents have a qualified higher educational status. In Figure 1, it is shown that 82.5% (47 answers) of the total number of respondents have a bachelor's degree, which is an indicator that people in business study at universities and have a higher level of education. Additionally, 2 respondents are getting a master's degree. While the other 10.5% (6 answers) are at the level of secondary school and yet, they also have an interest in startups.

It was also important to note the reason for creating a startup project (Figure 1). 40.4% of respondents prefer to be their own boss, while the remaining 28.1% of respondents are themselves interested in a particular product, and the remaining 24.6% want to try themselves in all areas, which is no less important for human development. There was also one interesting response in the column where respondents could add their own reasons for starting a startup: "Making money by hustling for yourself/your own benefit (being your own boss and not reporting to anyone but yourself) and of course be on track of your passion, be in-line with market opportunities of the 21st century (especially in the digital world/era)." According to this answer, it can definitely be noted that a person knows exactly what he wants.

In a startup, the most important role is the idea. For this reason, it shows how many respondents already have ideas, which creates opportunities for creating a developing startup. More than half noted that they already have ideas, while the remaining almost 40%, that is 23 participants, noted that there is no idea yet or it is not yet finished.

Of the 57 respondents, 36 of them have family business experience, while the remaining 21 do not. While 46 respondents out of the total number have experience in private enterprises, and the rest do not have it.

Of the 57 respondents, 43 said that it is very important to study the market and their rivals before opening their own project, and the rest think that this is not very important. According to respondents, for the success of a new venture (at an early stage) it is more important for an entrepreneur to develop an analytical business plan (45 responses), as well as spend time researching the market (31 responses), follow a detailed planning procedure (27 responses), and make a cost estimate for a new enterprise (23 answers). From the answers in

¹ author's development

Figure 5, it is possible to understand that the business plan is important, which also confirms the answers to the previous question.

Among the sources of funding, many respondents chose personal investments. Venture capital was also popular, and some would prefer to take bank loans and win state grants from the government (Figure 2).

What funding sources are you considering for your project?

Figure 2. Funding sources²

When asked how much their initial investment would be, everyone answered differently. There were amounts from 300 to 350,000 dollars. But basically, many respondents wrote that \$10,000 would be enough to open their own project.

In order to understand how many people want to scale their project, a question was asked about where they plan to establish their startup project. 70.2% answered in Tashkent, while 15.8% of respondents answered in all regions of Uzbekistan. Also, 7% of people answered that they would like to expand their project in the CIS countries. One participant wrote that he would set up his startup in Dubai to further expand his idea into the global market.

One of the main questions that needed to be answered was what challenges startups face in Uzbekistan and what factors they depend on. To this, the respondents answered in different ways, also including their own answers to this question. As can be seen, many noted that there is a lack of government support and funding. They also wrote that the team, young age, not enough market research, and not coping with capital turnover are the reasons for failure (Figure 3).

In your opinion, what problems do startups face in Uzbekistan and what factors do they depend on?

Figure 3. Difficulties of startups in Uzbekistan³

When asked what keeps them from developing their project to a larger level, many answered finances and lack of confidence in themselves and their ideas.

² author's development

³ author's development

After analyzing this, one can understand that fear and money are very closely related, because if a person himself is not sure of himself and his idea, then how can someone else believe in him and invest money.

It was also important to find out the opinion of people about whether it is difficult to develop a startup business to the international level in Uzbekistan, to which 57.9% of the respondents answered that yes, it is difficult, and the remaining 42.1% answered that they did not know about it.

It was also important to find out how long respondents are willing to wait before they see a profit from their business. Of the 57 respondents, 31 answered from 6 months to one year, the remaining 11 answered from 3 to 6 months, while the remaining 10 respondents answered from one year to one and a half years, and 5 people answered more than two and a half years.

When asked whether respondents are ready to invest their time and money in their project, and whether they are ready for the possibility of failure, more than 80% of respondents answered that they are ready for anything to get the desired result.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the determinants of startup development in Uzbekistan using a quantitative approach. The findings highlight several important factors that influence the success and growth potential of startups.

First, financial constraints were identified as one of the most significant challenges. Many respondents indicated that access to funding remains limited, which restricts the ability to launch and scale business ventures.

Second, the results emphasize the importance of market research and business planning. A large proportion of respondents acknowledged that understanding the market and developing a structured business plan are critical for startup success.

Third, entrepreneurial motivation and independence emerged as key drivers. Many participants expressed a strong desire to be self-employed and pursue their own business ideas, indicating a growing entrepreneurial mindset among young people in Uzbekistan.

Additionally, government support and institutional factors were perceived as important but still developing. While recent reforms have improved the business environment, further development of support mechanisms is needed.

The study also reveals that lack of confidence and fear of failure, alongside financial limitations, act as barriers to startup development. These psychological factors highlight the need for not only financial but also educational and mentoring support.

Overall, the findings suggest that startup development in Uzbekistan is influenced by a combination of economic, institutional, and personal factors. Strengthening access to finance, improving entrepreneurial education, and enhancing support systems could significantly contribute to the growth of the startup ecosystem.

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Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

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EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

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